

ISic1201

I.Sicily inscription 1201

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR150013

1. Ίουνίου

2. Φιλήμο

3. νος

Edition: PHI140685

1. Ίουνίου

2. Φιλήμο-

3. νος.

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492805

EDR 150013

EDCS 39101565

PHI 140685

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0378 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 200
Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 60-61 no.8

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